

plants) and seed rate (20 kg/ha) for pigeonpea single crop and intercrops were the same.

Single crop rice was direct seeded at 100 kg seed/ha in 15-cm rows. Intercropped rice, seeded at 75 kg seed/ha, had 60-cm row spacing.

Fertilizer was applied at 60 kg N, 13 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha.

All P and K and 25% N were applied basally. The remaining N was applied to rice 50% at 20 d and 25% at 40 d after seeding.

Grain yields were 1.8 t/ha for single

crop rice and 1.4 t/ha for intercropped rice (see table). Mean pigeonpea yield was 1.9 t/ha for single crop and 1.2 t/ha for the intercrop. The mean land equivalent ratio was 1.5, indicating considerable increase in resource use efficiency. □

A rice - grain legume cropping system for South Coastal Orissa, India

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We studied yields of five rice - grain legume cropping systems with varying fertilizer levels. The dry season crops were green gram *Vigna radiata*, black gram *Vigna mungo*, cowpea *Vigna*

unguiculata, peanut *Arachis hypogaea*, and wheat *Triticum aestivum*. No crop (fallow) was maintained for one treatment to study the nutrient uptake of wet season rice.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 5.63, 0.25% organic C, 95 kg available P (Bray)/ha, and 375 kg exchangeable K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications, with crops in the main plots and N levels in the subplots. Rice variety Pratap was transplanted on 10 Aug 1986 at 20- × 10-cm spacing with 40-60 kg

PK/ha applied as basal. N was applied in 2 splits at 0, 30, 60, and 90 kg/ha. Harvest was on 19 Nov 1986.

Dry season crops were sown 26 Dec 1986. Grain legumes and peanut received 20-40-0 and wheat 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the P and K was basal, the remaining N was topdressed 20 d after sowing. Preflowering and postflowering irrigations facilitated growth.

Rice - peanut and rice - black gram had the highest total grain yields, closely followed by rice - wheat (Table 1).

Total rice grain yield increased with N, but there was no significant difference between 60 kg N/ha and 90 kg N/ha.

Soil organic C percentage increased with the cropping patterns (Table 2). Available P and exchangeable K decreased in rice - black gram (which had the highest total grain production). □

Table 1. Grain yield of wet season rice and succeeding dry season crops. Orissa, India, 1986-87.

Cropping system	Wet season rice grain yield (t/ha)	Dry season crop grain yield (t/ha)	Total grain produced (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Total return (\$/ha)	Total profit (\$/ha)	Cost-benefit ratio
Rice - cowpea (C-152)	3.9	0.68	4.50	676	953	277	1.41
Rice - green gram (Berhampur local)	4.0	0.26	4.23	583	768	185	1.32
Rice - wheat (Sonalika)	4.0	0.61	4.59	722	900	178	1.25
Rice - black gram (T-9)	4.4	0.68	5.07	600	1048	448	1.74
Rice	4.3	—	4.29	478	686	208	1.43
Rice - peanut (Ak 12-24)	4.1	1.07	5.13	820	1244	423	1.52
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	0.32	—	—	—	—
<i>N levels</i>							
No N	3.6	0.52	4.10	—	—	—	—
30 kg N/ha	4.1	0.54	4.63	—	—	—	—
60 kg N/ha	4.2	0.57	4.81	—	—	—	—
90 kg N/ha	4.4	0.56	4.98	—	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	0.1	ns	0.14	—	—	—	—

Table 2. Soil test value after dry season crop. Orissa, India, 1986-87.

Cropping system	pH	Organic C (%)	Available P (kg/ha)	Exchangeable K (kg/ha)
Rice - cowpea	5.57	0.43	125	255
Rice - green gram	5.35	0.31	161	342
Rice - wheat	5.40	0.28	125	242
Rice - black gram	5.65	0.30	137	155
Rice - fallow (no crop)	5.70	0.33	147	227
Rice - peanut	5.60	0.35	125	227
Initial soil test value	5.63	0.25	95	375

Rice-based cropping sequences for northwestern Himalayas uplands

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We compared 7 irrigated upland rice-based intensive cropping sequences with traditional rice - wheat/potato sequences on VPKAS experimental fields (1,250 m). The experiment was conducted 1982-85 in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Three cycles were completed.

Soil was loamy with neutral pH and medium fertility. Recommended